

Artificial Intelligence Lifting Burden Of Justice Delivery System In India

Asst. Prof. Kaveri Aditya Deo

DES's Shri Navalmal Firodia Law College, Pune.

Email:ID: pljoshi275@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Supreme Court of India is deploying Artificial Intelligence and Machine learning based tools for case management. Such tools are used for transcribing oral arguments in constitution bench matters and such transcribed arguments can be accessed from the website of Supreme Court of India. In present century AI plays vital role in justice revolution. Talking about the Registry of Supreme Court of India, AI and Machine learning tools are been utilized for translating judgments from English to 18 different Indian languages. Considering such rapid use of AI in justice delivery system the question arises as to utmost care to be taken by the judges of Supreme Court while using such tools. This paper aims to discuss the AI assistance in justice delivery system in India and to study the challenges which may occur due to misuse. The author has tried to portray the differentiation between the Artificial intelligence and Human Intelligence to resolve the dispute. Author has tried to analyze the positive and negative side of use of AI for ease of justice in India.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Ease of Justice, Justice Revolution, Machine Learning Tools, Transcribed Arguments

INTRODUCTION:

It is generally stated that number of cases and number of judges do not match in Indian Judicial System. This results into pendency of cases. Considering the pendency of cases and the requirement of speedy disposal, there is a need of assistance of technology. Such assistance can be done through an Artificial Intelligence (hereinafter AI). Use of AI has always been questioned in different sectors. When AI was introduced it created positive impact on various sectors but slowly people started getting about the misuse of AI for personal gain, fraud etc. In Indian justice delivery system, pending cases are more as compare to number of judges. One can rely on AI when it comes to searching different information, ideas etc. but what about justice delivery system? This paper gives idea about the aid of AI in justice delivery system in India. The researcher has used doctrinal research method for data collection purpose. This paper explains the use of AI by Indian Judicial System, how such technology has been implemented in resolving the disputes and what different tools are used in procedural aspects. The paper aims to study the use of AI in Indian Judicial System and to understand various aspects related to same.

1. Rational and Significance of Artificial Intelligence in Indian Courtrooms

Artificial Intelligence has become the helping tool for each sector. One cannot completely rely upon the AI but can take help of AI to reduce the work burden. In case of courts the AI can assist in different manner such as searching tool, translator, research tool etc. Understanding the significance of AI, it is more useful for the courtrooms, judges, and advocates. The ultimate result of which is the

speedy disposal of trials. If the cases are resolved in such a speed then it will reduce the pendency and burden over the courts. The AI assist the courtrooms in data protection, legal research and data storage tool.

2. Artificial Intelligence Reshaping Justice Delivery System

As stated by the Chief Justice of India D.Y. Chandrachud, "technology is relevant in so far as it fosters efficiency, transparency and objectivity in public government. AI is present to provide a facilitative tool to judges in order to recheck or evaluate the work, the process, and the judgments".

Our judicial system is facing various issues such as pendency of cases, language barriers and the need of reformation through the acceptance of technology. We also need some technologies which are AI powered, such as machine learning, predictive analysis, natural language processing etc. Our judicial system has recently accepted the technology of AI for justice delivery system. One of the most important example is e-court project which was initiated under the aegis of Supreme Court of India.

Following are the AI based technologies used by judicial system. The ultimate purpose behind use of AI is speedy disposal of cases, case tracking, crime prevention etc.

a) Legal Translation and Language Accessibility

Indian Judiciary primarily works in English language mostly in High Courts and The Supreme Court. Such language preference may create barriers for those litigants who are non-English. AI-driven legal translation tools are being deployed in India to make legal documents and judgments accessible. Presently AI has translated more than 30 thousand Supreme Court Judgments into 16

regional languages including the languages such as Hindi, Tamil, Marathi, Kannada etc. The basic objective behind the use of such tools is nothing but accessibility. All the judgments should be accessible to all the states in India. There should be no language barrier on reading any judgment as ultimately justice delivery is an object.

b) Automated Case Management

AI driven tools will assist the courts for arranging the procedure of case management. Such technology will create the sequencing of caseloads to prioritize the cases as per the need of dispute resolution. Sometimes burden of different cases creates confusion and results in mismanagement of case preference. AI tool assists to create a sequence of such cases to avoid mismanagement and give preference to the appropriate case. It further will assist to schedule and monitor the dates of cases and reduce the burden over courts. This will ultimately result into smooth and systematic workflow of management.

c) Use of AI in Legal Research and Documentation

The most important assistance required to the judges is legal research. While settling any dispute in a court the judges always need an information from statutes, case laws or landmark judgments and any other relevant document. Such AI tools will assist in the court procedure to find out such information from vast database. It will speed up the procedure of legal research in court matters. It also may have negative consequences where such AI tool will be utilized to misuse particular documentation. E.g. signature change, date change or change in name etc. creating such changes with the help of AI will hamper the justice delivery system. Due to such reason the use of AI is sometimes questionable.

d) AI Assisted Filing and Court Procedure

The integration of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) and Natural Language Processing (NLP) is revolutionizing document digitization. These technologies automate the filing of court documents ensuring faster processing and reducing manual errors in the documentation process. NLP provides interpretation of human language. Such technology can be used to summarize the case documents. It also assist in analyzing the legal arguments and extracting the important information out of it e.g. ROSS Intelligence technology. Technology cannot take a place of human mind always. Sometimes interpretation of human language may not be correct with the help of AI tool. Such misinterpretation may result into the negative impact on court proceedings and justice to the just one. Interpretation up to a certain limit is justified but not always. AI may assist to summarize the case document but what if it leaves scope for ambiguity? It may leave scope for not covering certain required facts in the summary. Such questions create doubt about use of such AI driven tools in court system.

e) AI for User Assistance and Chatbots

AI assistance and chatbots provides real time information to the litigants. Such as current status of the case, guidance with respect to procedure and legal updates. This results into more user friendly tool for judicial system. Those

who are not familiar with the legal procedure can easily access the information through such technology. Such chatbots helps to provide real time information but for that reason someone i.e. human being will have to update the same on software then only same will be reflected on the AI application. Ultimately the human mind will have to work on it to create real time update to the litigants.

f) Use of AI for Predictive Analysis in Case Outcomes

AI technology can be utilized to analyze the historical landmark judgments and case study to offer predictive opinions about the case. It also helps to assess the risk and outcome in the case. This technology will help the judiciary to formulate the more precise decision in a case. Such technology contributes in judicial framework for predictive analysis and also helps to reduce the burden of a court. Predictive analysis may be a threatful tool on the other side. The word prediction itself suggest that “what may happen”. This tools just gives the prediction on the basis of data previously uploaded on the software but it may not always be correct and judge may not always rely upon the same. Such lacunas states that the AI tool may be ambiguous and may not be relevant always. Sometimes the judges gives decision on the basis of present need and requirement of the societal aspect. Such decisions are not always dependent upon previous judgments.

3. Digital Growth and Development of Indian Judiciary

1. Supreme Court Vidhik Anuvaad Software (SUVAS)

Presently the High Courts are proposing to launch Digital Law Reports and they are inviting applications for preparation of Head-notes for the Judgments. This SUVAS is an official application created to translate the legal documents and orders which are written in English into 9 vernacular languages. This AI based tool is released by The Supreme Court of India. Use of AI tool to translate the legal document may leave scope for ambiguity in the document. Such ambiguity may create the confusion in the mind of judiciary as well as litigant. It may result into new chapter of litigation on the basis of false document. Hence sometimes it is questionable to rely completely upon such documents.

2. Supreme Court Portal for Assistance in Court's Efficiency (SUPACE)

This is another AI based tool launched by the Supreme Court which collects the relevant legislation and facts related to the case and makes them available to the judges whenever they need it. This application helps in legal research, it reduces workload and analyses the data properly. Use of AI tool in legal research is mostly acceptable as it reduces the burden on judges, it saves time of courts and litigants. AI assistance to find legal term, case law, legal provisions, circulars and notification etc. is completely acceptable and has no scope for any vagueness.

3. Kira Systems by Cyril Amarchand Mangaldas

By collaboration with Canadian AI helper Kira Systems, Indian company Cyril Amarchand Mangaldas is now using AI for contract analysis and review. In standard forms of contract AI assistance may be taken to save time and to create uniformity in the documents.

CONCLUSION

Artificial Intelligence analyzes different crime patterns, high risk areas and can also predict further in case. Such technology can also be used for surveillance and investigation purpose where automated drones can be used to monitor and suspect tracking. One most important example of AI in Judicial system is E-court project. Where it provides the track record of the case proceedings and easily accessible to all. Talking about examining evidences and digital crime trails, the AI based forensic

analysis can be used. Artificial Intelligence is transforming India's judiciary and law enforcement by enhancing case management, legal research, crime prevention, and language accessibility. With sustained government investment and regulatory oversight, AI has the potential to make India's justice system faster, more accessible, and transparent for all citizens. As per the authors point of view use of AI in standard legal format, legal research, e-courts etc. is justified but the scope for loopholes maybe there when it comes to predictive analysis, translation in different languages etc. Hence it can be stated that, 'it is not always the Artificial Intelligence but the Human Mind plays vital role in court proceedings

REFERENCES

- 1 Miss. Deepthi P D & Smt. Sheela Ganesh (2023). Interface Between Artificial Intelligence and Information Technology in The Justice System: An Analysis, *JSS Journal for Legal Studies and Research*, 9(2), 64 -74 <https://jsslawcollege.in/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/5.-Interface-Between-AI-and-IT-in-the-Justice-System-An-Analysis.pdf>.
- 2 Ministry of Law and Justice. (2025, February 25). Digital Transformation of Justice: Integrating AI in India's Judiciary and Law Enforcement. [Press Release] <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=2106239®=3&lang=2>.
- 3 Dharampuri District Court. (2024, March). SUVAS – Supreme Court Vidhik Anuvaad Software – High Court has proposed to launch Digital Law Reports – High Court invites application for preparation of Head-notes for the Judgments. Dharampuri District Court, E-Courts Mission Mode Projects. <https://dharampuri.dcourts.gov.in/suvas-supreme-court-vidhik-anuvaad-software-high-court-has-proposed-to-launch-digital-law-reports-high-court-invites-application-for-preparation-of-head-notes-for-the-judgments/>.
- 4 Navneet Kaur, Manpreet Kaur (2024). Role of artificial intelligence in the Indian courts, *International Journal of Law, Policy and Social Review*, 6(1), 17-20. <https://www.lawjournals.net/archives/2024/vol6/issue1/5124>